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Report on Subsidized Organic Groceries in Lunetten

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Report on Subsidized Organic Groceries in Lunetten: Executive Summary

Project Overview:

The Organic Subsidized Groceries project in Lunetten, spanning from June to November 2023, aimed to provide affordable access to organic groceries. Led by Ineke Malsch and Elizabete Fedčenko, the project distributed vouchers funded by municipality of Utrecht, the Katholieke Caritas Utrecht and part of the Mantel van Sint Maarten 2022 third prize, allowing residents to redeem them at Ekovers and Koppelsteede. Vouchers were distributed in the community center and giveaway shop Limoenz - Treek 15 in Utrecht-Lunetten.

Results:

The project demonstrated high participant engagement, distributing vouchers on specific dates at the local community center, Limoenz. Feedback and interviews revealed significant interest in sustainable living, with an emphasis on the quality and health benefits of organic produce. However, key challenges surfaced, primarily centered around price, accessibility, atmosphere, and the need for education and transparency.

Challenges Identified:

- 1) *Price:* Affordability of organic groceries was a recurring concern, with participants expressing a desire to balance ideals with budget constraints.
- 2) *Accessibility and Convenience:* Participants highlighted the inconvenience of accessing organic groceries, suggesting a need for increased availability in larger supermarket chains.
- 3) *Atmosphere:* The visual appeal and atmosphere of organic stores were noted, indicating a preference for welcoming aesthetics.
- 4) *Education and Transparency:* Lack of information about sustainable living and the origin of products emerged as a significant theme, calling for more education and transparency in stores.

Suggestions for Future Initiatives:

- 1) *Buy 1 Give 1 Project*: Inspired by successful models elsewhere, explore initiatives where customers purchase extra organic produce for those in need, enhancing accessibility and reducing costs.
- 2) *Improving Atmosphere of Organic Shops*: Encourage organic stores to enhance their visual appeal, making them more welcoming to a diverse community, potentially boosting both atmosphere and affordability.
- 3) *Food Pass Project*: Emulate successful models like Rotterdam's food pass, providing people on low incomes with the flexibility to choose their groceries, reducing food waste and offering more choice.
- 4) *Involving Shop Associations*: Collaborate with shop associations to provide bonus cards for organic products, funded by business taxes, promoting sustainable businesses and supporting lower-income individuals.
- 5) *Expanding Community Centers*: Increase funding for community centers to expand their functions beyond giveaways, incorporating educational events on sustainable living, cooking classes, and workshops.
- 6) *Addressing Fragmentation of Policies*: Explore solutions to overcome the fragmentation of resources, ensuring that even those above certain income thresholds can access support for sustainable living.

Introduction

This report contains the results and analysis of the project on Subsidized Organic Groceries in the neighbourhood Lunetten. This project was taking place from June 2023 to November 2023 and was led by Ineke Malsch - the founder of organisation Duurzaam Utrecht 2030 - and Elizabete Fedčenko - an intern from University College Utrecht who joined in September 2023. This project was a continuation of previous research, entitled 'Duurzaam Utrecht 2030 - subsidizing organic and sustainable fruit and vegetables' by Jinte van Eijk, Teun Hartstra, Tymen Swets, Niels Hoevenberg and Maud Rampaart (Environmental Science students at HAS University of Applied Sciences). These students produced multiple possible systems to deliver sustainable food to residents with a small budget - one of them being using subsidies by the municipality to purchase vouchers from organic grocery store Ekovers in the Lunetten neighbourhood. This trial was made possible in part by subsidies from the Initiative Fund of the municipality of Utrecht, the Katholieke Caritas Utrecht and part of the third prize of the Mantel van Sint Maarten 2022. The goal of this project was to gather input from people with low income regarding organic groceries and what problems they have encountered with sustainable living to understand how to induce meaningful bottom up change as well as make recommendations to the municipality. This report outlines the main findings from the collected feedback and interviews as well as workable solutions and recommendations for other organisations, local businesses, and the municipality of Utrecht.

Description of the project

The following steps were taken by Ineke Malsch to organize this project for which the results this report is focused on. In collaboration with the previously mentioned organic grocery store Ekovers as well as another established contact in the previous project - Utrecht Natuurlijk location Koppelsteede and with funding received from the Initiative Fund and the Catholic Caritas Utrecht, 10-euro worth vouchers were bought at Ekovers and Koppelsteede. These were given out starting from June 2023 once a month on Tuesdays in a local community centre Limoenz. In September Elizabete Fedčenko joined the project and the visits to community centre Limoenz. She also made some additional visits, including some on Thursdays. The voucher giveaway events took place on 13th of June, 4th of July, 1st of August 5th and 7th of September 3rd and 17th of October. The visitors of the community centre were mostly older people, and people who had recently moved to the Netherlands. It is an important organization in the neighbourhood as it functions as a giveaway shop where people can bring things they do not need anymore, and visitors can pick up what they need or want for free. It is also crucial in fostering the neighbourhood community and is a place where people can connect and learn about each other as well as relevant initiatives in the neighbourhood.

Along with receiving a voucher from one of the shops, participants were also given a leaflet/ questionnaire (Appendix 2) with the most important information about the project and

a couple of questions on their experience such as “What did you purchase?”; “Were you happy with the experience and products?”; “Do you want to buy more organic groceries and what is stopping you?”, “Do you have any suggestions for the municipality on how to solve these problems?”; “Do you have any other tips or comments?”. Along with the physical questionnaire participants were urged to come give their feedback during our next visit at Limoenz and have a more general conversation about what they think about sustainable living, how they already try to be more sustainable, what problems they have encountered and how they think they could be solved. After collecting all the feedback, we went back to Limoenz on 7th of November for a final open discussion on what we have found so far and the suggestions we had produced. On 27th of November there was also a brainstorming session organized at Social Impact Factory on the same topic of accessible sustainable groceries with some students and a representative from BuurtBuik - another local organisation focused on providing sustainable and accessible food in neighbourhoods around Utrecht.

The aim of this research project was to do qualitative research into what the opinions and problems of people with a smaller budget are regarding sustainable living. An important focus of this research project was to have honest, meaningful conversations with the people who struggle the most with accessing sustainable living and seeing what their wants and needs are rather than trying to impose a solution from above. The project originally focused on organic food specifically based on the recommendations of people interviewed in spring 2022. Throughout the trial with the vouchers, some people still said they preferred organics, while others placed more emphasis on fresh and healthy food in general. In any case, the project aims to address the SDGs where all three varieties are relevant.

Results and analysis

Below you can see an overview of our visits to Limoenz giveaway shop, how many people we talked to and what kind of items they purchased with the vouchers.

Day	Ekovers vouchers	Koppelstee de vouchers	Number of feedback received	fresh produce	other food/drink	other items
13th of June	25	7	0			
4th of July	33	5	16	3	8	2
1st of August	11	8	15-20	3	8	2
September 5 and 7, and 17	25	10	17			

October 3 and 17	31	10	18			
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After analysis of the collected feedback and conversations a clearly notable observation is that everyone, we talked to is interested and motivated to lead a more sustainable life. This was an issue that all participants had something to say about, and they had clearly thought about it before. Regarding organic groceries specifically, most participants noted down the better quality, taste, and healthiness of the purchased items. It is important to note that the following analysis of results includes not only organic groceries but accessing a more sustainable way of eating in general as that is what many participants were bringing up.

Besides the clear presence of motivation and interest we have identified four main themes / areas of possible improvement that kept coming up in the conversations with participants.

Price

This was undoubtedly the most mentioned obstacle for buying organic groceries and living more sustainably in general. Many participants said that they would love to go to stores like Ekovers, but the price is not appropriate for their budget. Some interviewees did not have the ability to consider what products are more sustainable or organic in their everyday lives - the question is often which is the cheapest option available. This leads to people with a smaller budget to have to choose between their ideals and money.

Accessibility and convenience

The second most key point brought up by an equal number of participants is the lack of accessibility of organic groceries. People with smaller budgets often have busier lives and less motivation to go out of their way to seek out organic groceries. This is why even for the vouchers; more people chose the Ekovers voucher as it is located near a shopping centre with other shops. A commonly heard comment was that people want more organic and sustainable food available in bigger supermarket chains - such as Albert Heijn, Lidl, Dirk, Jumbo and others. There are a lot of areas of improvement in bigger supermarket chains such as avoiding plastic packaging for produce, dealing with food waste of products that are “not up to standard,” highlighting organic products and produce more, offering better deals for lower income people and so on.

This is not to say that improvements and progress are only to be done with these bigger players in the field - it would be supplementary to improvements and projects coming from smaller local organizations and businesses. The combination of improved price points and accessibility is crucial to any practical solutions.

Atmosphere

An unexpected number of people mentioned the aspect of atmosphere and their experience while shopping as well. For example, Ekovers visitors mentioned how the atmosphere of the shop is not particularly welcoming and the proportion of fresh produce to other products in the store seems paradoxical for an organic store that focuses on providing sustainable food. To be clear, this does not pertain to the service provided or the employees in the store but rather the visuals and aesthetic of these stores. This was also discussed in the brainstorm session on 27th of November - it was concluded that most organic supermarkets in the city have a “beige” aesthetic to it that seems aimed at a certain group of community (mostly those with higher income). Some participants mentioned that they would be more inclined to go into organic supermarkets if there was more focus on the fresh produce, more colour and variety seen from the entrance and inside the store.

On the other hand, the visitors of Koppelsteede highly valued the additional aspect of a petting zoo and cafe alongside the ability to purchase organic products. This shows that accessible community and leisure activities are highly valued by participants - taking this into account when thinking of solutions can be helpful.

Education and transparency

Last notable theme identified in the interviews was the lack of education and transparency on where our food comes from and how it is produced. In terms of education there is a general interest expressed in how exactly to eat more sustainably, conveniently, and affordably, what are the differences between organic, sustainable, and regular products, how to approach different dietary restrictions with a smaller budget and so on. In terms of transparency there was an interest in making it more clear in shops where products are coming from and how they were produced.

Solutions and suggestions

There is a wide range of practical solutions and steps to take forward to make sustainable living possible for lower income communities. The solutions and suggestions described below focus on one or more of the main themes identified in the results and analysis section. The first couple of points are more focused on local small-scale initiatives for interested NGOs, organizations as well as organic shops.

1) Buy one give one project.

Focusing on the themes of price and accessibility, this idea is inspired by similar projects taking place in other countries where regular visitors of shops or cafes are

encouraged to buy an extra product for someone else. In this case the focus would be on fresh organic produce specifically. The paid for products can then be distributed in a variety of ways:

- Once week organic supermarkets make a delivery of the fresh produce to local food banks.
- The receipt is placed in the window of the store indicating that there is free fresh produce available in the store that someone else has paid for.

This can also be approached in a way where customers of organic shops can purchase a voucher for someone else, the vouchers then get delivered to community centres or food banks and are available for its visitors - this approach provides a higher element of choice for the participants but also decreases the convenience and accessibility aspect as people would have to visit the stores themselves. This project is something Duurzaam Utrecht 2030 is going to explore more in detail in the following months.

2) *Improving atmosphere of organic shops in neighbourhoods*

As mentioned in the results section, the unwelcoming atmosphere and visuals of some organic supermarkets is something to consider for any business owners. Many interviewees brought up Turkish, Persian, or other stores in the city as an alternative - these stores are not focused on providing organic food specifically, but they do have a strong focus on fresh produce, and they display it in the store and by the entrance in a way that is welcoming to passers by. Improving the atmosphere of organic stores in combination with price incentives would provide a win-win situation both for the shops themselves and the local community.

The following suggestions are more focused on municipal involvement and funding.

3) *Food pass project*

In Rotterdam, experiments have been conducted with a food pass that allows people on low incomes to buy their own groceries. The Rotterdam Food Bank is currently switching to four food bank supermarkets instead of the traditional distribution points:

<https://voedselbank.nl/over-ons>. The idea is that depending on the income, households receive a food pass and a list of how many items they can get from each section - then they can go to special food bank supermarkets to put together their own package. This involves a higher element of choice for the people in need and reduces food waste even more. A few years ago, the Utrecht city council passed a motion to do the same in Utrecht, but there was no follow-up at the political level: <https://www.ad.nl/utrecht/groenlinks-christenunie-en-pvda-willen-onderzoek-naar-voedselpas-voor-mensen-met-laag-inkomen~a1099f44/>. There already is a similar food bank supermarket in Leidsche Rijn as in Rotterdam: <https://voedselbankplusleidscherijn.nl/>. This has been well received and we would like this project to gain a fresh start - for this there is a need for municipality funding and manpower to establish. Currently there is a difficulty in transforming already existing food banks into supermarkets because the locations are often used by other organizations or purposes for half of the time. This solution would tackle the problems of price, accessibility and convenience and give more freedom of choice to people in need.

4) Involving shop associations in neighbourhoods

Addressing both the price and the accessibility and convenience themes is a suggestion to approach shop associations of certain neighbourhoods / streets for a more systematic approach to solving the problem. As organizations must pay a business tax to the municipality and these funds are used for improving the respective neighbourhoods, it would be a promising idea to apply these funds for providing continuous bonus cards for organic and sustainable products for stores. For example, there are already available bonus cards that can be purchased for 12,50 EUR in Albert Heijn to get 10% off the sustainable line of their products. Making something like this freely available to lower income people would be helpful. Additionally, funds can be used to promote organic supermarkets or other sustainable businesses in the neighbourhood by providing discount codes / vouchers - this would help both participants and the businesses.

5) Expanding the function and funding of community centres

As we have noticed throughout this trial in Lunetten and more specifically after visiting the giveaway shop Limoenz so many times community centres can serve several extremely valuable roles in the neighbourhoods. As mentioned before, it is a place where to exchange clothes and other items, a meeting and socializing location where people can interact with their neighbours and share information and it can also be used as a potential centre of education on topics like affordable and sustainable living. During the conducted interviews there was an expressed interest in expanding the function of community centres for educational events on sustainable and affordable eating as well as simple meal cooking classes, communal dinners, workshops on growing herbs for example and so on. As community centres are usually volunteer run, there would need to be increased funding from the municipality to realize these ambitions, but we believe it would be highly valuable.

6) Fragmentation of policies

Lastly, another solution that we have produced is dealing with the fragmentation of policies and helpful resources that are available for people in need. Although there are some great resources available such as U-Pas, there are many people who do not qualify for this pass because they are just above the income level or for other reasons. Additionally, with inflation and increasing cost of living it is becoming increasingly hard to live comfortably with all the necessities. Although it is understandable why there needs to be certain criteria for resources like the U-Pas, we think that it is important to consider all people who cannot afford a sustainable lifestyle into these future solutions. Currently there are many other things that people might prioritize before sustainable and healthy food even though it is one of the most key factors for both the health of humans and the environment. This is just an observation we have made, not something we have investigated in detail so further research on how to integrate and expand existing resources should be done.

Appendix 1: All previous reports

Trial with subsidized organic groceries in Lunetten, June-December 2023.

Try organic groceries yourself - Tell us what you think - And share your tips for what could be improved.

Report of meeting at the limoenz foundation giveaway shop, 4 July 2023, 9.00-12.00 hrs. By Ineke Malsch, ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl

On June 13, I had distributed twenty-five gift vouchers of ten euros from the Ekovers supermarket to visitors of the giveaway shop, plus four vouchers from the Horeca van Utrecht Natuurlijk (location Koppelsteede). The coordinator of the Food Bank Lunetten had also handed out three vouchers from the Horeca van Utrecht Natuurlijk. They were regular gift cards that customers of both stores can also give as gifts. I had given the recipients an A4 with an explanation of the project and some questions, and asked if they would answer these questions orally or in writing next time (July 4). On July 4, I spoke to sixteen people about the receipts I had handed out on June 13. I handed out thirty-three new vouchers and a returned voucher from Ekovers plus five from Utrecht Natuurlijk. One person exchanged his voucher from Ekovers for one from Utrecht Natuurlijk. I gave this voucher from Ekovers to someone else. Three receipts were lost. The recipient promised to search again.

Most people had bought food or drinks or both. One person had bought bamboo socks and a family had also bought personal care products. Most were satisfied, but some doubted whether the foods were tastier than non-organic products. Some used to buy organic products or bought organic products in the supermarket if they were on sale. Several people found the products expensive (see table). One person answered the question 'What can the municipality of Utrecht do to help you buy organic groceries?': The gardens of Utrecht Natuurlijk already belong to the municipality of Utrecht. I get to volunteer there. It is fun to work in the garden.

Two people made other comments:

- I often eat vegetarian. You can also protect the environment or your health by not smoking and not drinking alcohol. Then it does not matter much whether you eat sprayed or unsprayed vegetables. My brother had an organic farm. I know from him that it is demanding work. If organic were as expensive as regular produce, I do not know if I would buy it. Rather, make a mix of organic and regular products. If you are short on money, it is not that important whether it is organic or not. The price for organic products must be reduced, otherwise no one wants to buy it. I worked at a biodynamic store. The products are full-fledged.
- People used to spend a larger part of their income on food. Now no one wants to pay for sustainable products.

Question:	What did you buy?	What do you think of the products?	Do you want to buy organic or sustainable groceries more often? What do you need for that?
1	Bamboo socks and something else small	The socks are good, absorbent, and permeable.	I have been to the store before. The products are too expensive for me. I usually do my shopping in the regular supermarket. There are sometimes eco-products on sale, then I buy them. For example, jasmine rice if it is on sale. I like to buy brown rice because it is healthier than white rice. ... When I bought organic, I was shocked by the price on the receipt.
2	Fruit	It tastes better than sprayed fruit but is pricey.	It is ideal that you can choose what you buy.
3 -6	Shampoo, cake, paracetamol, toothpaste, face cream, bread	We were satisfied with it.	
7	Monastery bread, cheese, blackberry-apple juice	It was very tasty. I imagine that the juice was tastier than juice from the supermarket, although I do not buy this kind of juice there. It tastes better because it was so expensive. The cheese was tasty, but expensive. I would not buy that cheese myself. The bread was also very tasty.	I would like to buy products there more often. I would like the bread, but I do not know if I can afford to buy it there every time. Someone helps me to gain insight into my budget because I don't have an overview myself. If I can afford it, I want to buy this bread more often.
8	Buttermilk, puff pastry, chestnut mushrooms.	It was good, nice to taste the products.	It is better if you can go to any store throughout the Netherlands.
9	Seasoning	Very tasty	

10	Now nothing	I visit Ekovers more often. They are friendly and you can have a nice chat and philosophize. At the location in park Transwijk of Utrecht Of course they have tasty things. A jar of honey can easily cost five euros.	You need enough budget. If it were less expensive, I would buy organic products more often.
11	Dried apricots, raisins, and pumpkin seeds for my daughter (a baby).	It is healthy and good for my daughter.	Albert Heijn would also be good. I often go shopping there. Ekovers does not have everything I need.
12	Pasta/spaghetti, tomatoes, oil, milk	It was good. Especially the pasta was affordable, other products I had wanted to buy were too expensive.	
13	Frozen paste and milk	My sister bought it and was satisfied	
14	Packaged young cheese	There was not much flavour to it. I do not know if it was tastier than the cheese from the supermarket. I do not buy loose cheese, because it dries out quickly.	I want to buy organic cheese again, but maybe not young cheese.
15	Not bought anything now, but experience with organic products	The taste of organic milk does make a lot of difference, and I tried a small jar of very tasty organic jam.	
16	Apricots	It is a nice shop.	I used to buy a lot of organic products, especially fruits and vegetables.

Trial with subsidized organic groceries in Lunetten, June-December 2023.

Try organic groceries yourself - Tell us what you think - And share your tips for what could be improved.

Report of meeting at the limoenz foundation's giveaway shop, 1 August 2023, 9.00-12.00 hrs. By Ineke Malsch, ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl

On 1 August, Anneke Boersma (Food Council Utrecht being established) and I asked 15-20 visitors their opinion about organic and sustainable groceries they had bought for previously distributed gift vouchers. Two people had drunk coffee with something tasty at Koppelsteede, one person was planning to buy fruit and vegetables when there was more new harvest. According to the saleswoman in the Catering of Koppelsteede, someone else had also bought a thermos cup. Most of them had bought food from Ekovers. Two people had bought cleaning supplies, and one person was planning to buy face cream if it wasn't too expensive. Most liked the products or liked them, although some preferred to do all the shopping at a supermarket at the same time. Vouchers from the Ekovers supermarket were more popular than from Koppelsteede because it was closer, and they were used to doing their shopping in the mall. Although the Ekovers is closed until August 15 because of the holidays, some preferred a voucher from it rather than from Koppelsteede. I handed out eleven new vouchers from Ekovers plus eight from Utrecht Natuurlijk. One person had lost a receipt. The recipient promised to search again. This was the third time I have handed out coupons. Read the reports of 13 June and 4 July here.

Do you want to buy organic or sustainable groceries more often? What do you need for that?

Responses to this question were divided. Some were very conscious about health, sustainability, or both, and bought as many organic or sustainable products as possible. Others bought the cheapest products or did all the shopping at a supermarket, where the price was especially important. Most people needed more money to be able to buy organic products more often, through a monthly subsidy or a discount voucher from the retailers. If the Hoogvliet and Albert Heijn supermarkets offered organic or regional products more often and provided more information about the origin of the product in the store, people would prefer that. Outside the holidays, the mobile packaging-free stall of Loos Utrecht drives through Lunetten on Fridays. Some had heard of it and wanted to go shopping there if it was affordable. A few people regularly picked up fruit and vegetables at the Koningshof or Moestuin Maarschalkerweerd. For others, that was too far.

What can the municipality of Utrecht do to help you buy organic groceries?

Not everyone had an opinion about what the municipality of Utrecht can do. A few people wanted a voucher for organic products every month. Others preferred organic products to be cheaper.

Do you have any other tips for us?

One person wanted a pass for 40-50% off organic and sustainable products. People also suggested involving other providers of organic, sustainable, or regional products, and collaborating with similar initiatives in Utrecht or other places.

Overview of the answers per person:

1. I bought two coffees, a pastry and ice cream with friends at Koppelsteede. I thought about buying cheese too. If I only buy it if it is free, the municipality is not going to pay for it. I like to buy all the groceries at once. The advantage of the farm is that it is a regional product. Am I going to buy it if it is also in Hoogvliet, is a question of conscience. I do not look to see if it is a regional product. The retailer can provide more information by putting a display cabinet in the store with information about where the products come from.

A gift voucher helps to see where the product comes from, if I had gone alone, but not with friends, like now. Only I do not go to the petting zoo. A friend of mine often goes alone. I did tell my friends that I had received a receipt. We often go to the petting zoo together. I do not remember exactly if we went because we often go to the petting zoo, or because I had a voucher.

If I go for a walk with the dog, I am not allowed to enter the petting zoo. That is a hindrance. I get it, the dog was already getting restless when we passed a meadow with sheep. It is more convenient if I can combine the walk with the dog and then immediately buy cheese. My mother used to always want to combine a walk and shopping. That is efficient.

I sometimes tell people that the Limoenz giveaway shop is there and that vouchers for organic products are distributed here.

2. I bought bread from Ekovers. It was very tasty. I would like to buy bread or milk more often because it is tastier. The Ekovers is convenient because it is close by.
3. What are organic groceries? What can you buy at Ekovers? Can you also buy face cream? I would like to buy it because I have sensitive skin. How expensive is it? The information is not on the store's website.
4. See the answers on paper. An additional suggestion for the Ekovers retailer is to give coupons to customers. I never come to Koppelsteede. I am satisfied with the products, they are much healthier, with more minerals. The food does not come from factory farming. I eat vegetarian, which also saves on costs. I also go to the Koningshof, where they grow fruit and vegetables without pesticides. It is puzzling. I would like to realize my ideals and buy healthier and more sustainable products. I must choose every time.
5. See table.
6. I received a receipt from Ekovers but lost it. I like to visit Limoenz, but also at the Lunetten junction, in Houten and at Bosshardt on Kanaleneiland. Healthy eating is important. I try to pay attention to that, but sometimes I am forced to eat unhealthy food. For example, my grandchildren would like to go to McDonalds. Around the Mediterranean, the menu is healthy.

7. See table.
8. Me and my husband both bought organic milk. Last time we both bought spaghetti, but it ran out. It would have been better if there were more foods because food is the basic need. Food is the most important thing.
9. I would like to buy fruit and vegetables at Koppelsteede, but they did not have much on offer yet. I am waiting for them to have new harvests.
10. See table.
11. Otherwise, I always go to Hoogvliet, that is the closest thing for me. AH is too expensive. Now I can buy extra tasty things, such as summer fruit. Otherwise, I buy apples and pears. Am I thinking about sustainability? I look at what is the cheapest. Sustainable should be the cheapest. An extra tenner is nice. You cannot buy much with AOW alone. Cranberries are otherwise too expensive.
12. I had a nice lunch at the petting zoo. The coffee with quiches and salad cost exactly ten euros. At the petting zoo they also have vegetables. I try to buy those anyway. I also have friends who have a garden, I get a lot of that. It is tasty and healthy. When I had more money, I also bought from Ecoplaza, but that is now too expensive. If you have a vegetable garden yourself, you can biologically fight aphids with green soap.
13. Ekovers is a very good store, where you can buy food and superfood. I bought cranberry jam, and clock dish soap. That is good for your hands. They also have tasty olives with cheese. It is worth spending money on it, but it is a bit expensive. You can buy very few. I do buy some from time to time. I also bought seeds for apple, eggplant, corn, zucchini, etc. I sent those seeds to Turkey. They were very grateful for that and so was I.

Other programs to like:

Loos Utrecht is a mobile shop that drives through Lunetten on Fridays outside the holidays and then stops at the shopping centre and at two more locations. They sell packaging-free organic products. Some visitors had already heard of it. There used to be a packaging-free shop in the Twijnstraat, but that is gone. It is probably too expensive. Why is that?

At de Koningshof you can also buy fruit and vegetables on Saturday. Some go there. Tuinderij Maarschalkerweerd also has a shop. The bread is very tasty. It is too far away for me. Some people are willing to get something tasty by bike, even on the Voorstraat, where they have tasty bread.

The Utrecht Food Council wants to make all activities related to food in the city visible to the municipality, especially the social aspect.

There is a link between health and organic. Sprayed foods are unhealthy. Unsprayed foods are healthier, but too expensive. At AH and other stores, you do have a small shelf with organic products. AH issues coupons (separate bonus card) for 12.50 with which you get a 10% discount on organic products. Can they make those coupons free for people with little money? Or give a card with which you can get a refund at

customer service when handing in receipts on which the organic products are indicated separately.

Tirza Andriessen is researching alternatives to the food bank. Rotterdam is doing a trial with a debit card with a credit with which people can do their own shopping. In Leidsche Rijn there is a food bank where people can choose healthy and organic products.

	Where?	What?	Satisfaction?	More often?	municipality	Tips
1	Koppelsteede	Two coffees, a pastry and ice cream	Yes, see detailed answer			
2	Ekovers	bread	Very tasty	yes		
3	Ekovers	Nothing yet				
4a	Ekovers	olive oil	good	Yes, more money	Give monthly vouchers for free	Give a pass for this, for example with a 40% or 50% discount
4b	Ekovers	Tahini, peanut butter, soy whipped cream (some extra charge)	good	More money	More vouchers, regular distribution	
5	Ekovers	Two bags of nut muesli, then the money ran out	Very tasty	Last time I had bought nice cheese		
6	Ekovers	lost				
7	Ekovers	Dishwashing liquid and all-purpose cleaner	Fine, they are biodegradable and smell nice	Not necessarily, but preferably yes.	It would be nice if the organic products became a bit cheaper.	?

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Report of the Meeting at the Giveaway Shop of the Limoenz Foundation, September 5, 2023, 10:00 AM - 1:00 PM and September 7, 2023, 10:00-12:00. By Ineke Malsch and Elisabete Fedčenko.

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On September 5th, we surveyed seventeen visitors of the Limoenz Foundation's giveaway shop for their opinions on organic and sustainable groceries they had purchased using previously distributed gift vouchers. We also spoke with a handful of other attendees about tips for making organic and sustainable products accessible to people with limited budgets. Thirteen people had done their shopping at Ekovers. Most of them had bought groceries, while a few had purchased laundry detergent, dish soap, or shampoo. Four people had received vouchers from Koppelsteede. Coffee with something on the side was the most popular choice. One person had bought cheese, and another planned to buy fresh vegetables from the new harvest. Opinions varied somewhat. Most were satisfied with the quality, but some found it underwhelming. Nearly everyone found the products to be expensive. Elisabete Fedčenko has been working with Duurzaam Utrecht 2030 since September 1st and is conducting research on subsidized organic groceries. We distributed thirteen new vouchers that allow people to buy organic groceries at the Ekovers supermarket, as well as five gift vouchers from the Koppelsteede urban farm of Utrecht Natuurlijk. This was the fourth time we distributed vouchers. Read more in the reports from June 13th, July 4th, and August 1st available from this webpage: <https://duurzaamutrecht2030.nl/en-gb/biobooodschappen> .

Would you like to buy organic or sustainable groceries more often? What do you need for that?

Convenience was a top priority for many people. If the regular supermarket where they do their daily shopping offered affordable organic products and they didn't have to search for them, they would be inclined to buy organic products. Most Koppelsteede visitors went there primarily for a cup of coffee or a visit to the petting zoo, rather than to buy vegetables, fruits, organic meat, or dairy.

What can the municipality of Utrecht do to help you buy organic groceries?

A few people mentioned suggestions for the municipality, but they also mentioned supermarkets and the national government as responsible organizations.

Do you have any other tips for us?

More attention to sustainability in schools.

Attention to people with diabetes.

At the Doordouwers community garden in Overvecht, there is a communal garden where local residents can garden themselves, guided by two members of the Doordouwers. There is also a similar communal vegetable garden in Transwijk Park.

Through the Thuisgekookt foundation, you can offer a self-cooked meal to someone else. They aim for long-term connections, where you cook for the same person every week, for example.

At the Limoenz Foundation's giveaway shop, they also want to have more communal meals or cooking sessions or even bake cakes together.

On the campus of University College Utrecht, an organization sells vegetable bags for 5-7 euros to students. They collaborate with local growers. These are organic vegetarian packages. I don't know if they are expensive or cheap, but they are very popular among students. Maybe something similar could be done in Lunetten.

Ekovers customers can also pick up a food bag from Odin on Thursdays, for which they have a weekly subscription.

On September 7th, Elizabete Fedčenko went to Limoenz Foundation giveaway shop from 10:00-12:00 to give out vouchers and talk to visitors about their thoughts and recommendations regarding organic grocery shopping for lower income communities. It was expected that different people might visit Limoenz on Thursday morning than on Tuesdays. No feedback on the vouchers was collected since people were not informed before that Elizabete will be coming on this day. 11 vouchers were given out to some new visitors who had not used the vouchers before and they were informed of our next visit times - including the Harvest festival at Koppelsteede on 17th of September. Elizabete had a longer conversation about organic groceries with one woman who had participated in the initiative a few months ago to gather general feedback on sustainable grocery shopping.

What did you think of this initiative in general?

I bought fruit and vegetables and they are much tastier than the ones from regular supermarkets. But it was way too expensive, you cannot buy enough food, especially for a family with kids.

Do you have any tips?

The fruit and vegetables there are too perfect in regular supermarkets, they all look like from a movie, it does not need to be that way. We would buy an apple with a few spots on it. There is also way too much plastic, everything is individually packaged. And it is all made for lazy people, vegetables are pre cut, cheese is pre grated and there are so many ready made meals available. This could be a change made in regular supermarkets. Additionally, having options in all stores to buy the perfect packaged fruit and vegetables, but also the less perfect ones and organic produce. Everyone wants to buy organic produce but it is just too expensive. Maybe a government subsidy on organic produce could be an option

Duurzaam UTRECHT

Visitors of Harverst festival live sustainably

Report of the Harvest festival at city farm Koppelsteede of Utrecht Natuurlijk, September 17, 2023, 1:00 PM - 5:00 PM. By Elizabete Fedčenko, e.fedcenko@students.uu.nl

Ineke behind the stand of Duurzaam Utrecht 2030.

On September 17th, Ineke Malsch and Elizabete had a stand at the Harvest festival taking place at Utrecht Natuurlijk Koppelsteede. At the stand we had informational posters on Duurzaam Utrecht 2030, our goals and activities so far.

How do people live sustainably?

We also asked visitors to add sticky notes under posters with two questions: “What are you doing to live more sustainably?” and “What do you want to do to live more sustainably?” 19 people answered the first question and 12 people answered the second question.

Analysis: The answers to the question “What are you doing to live more sustainably?” covered a lot of topics and only a couple of answers overlapped - mostly ones about solar panels and insulation. This shows that education on sustainability was at a somewhat good level for the visitors of the festival. The question “What do you want to do to live more sustainably” also addressed a wide range of problems: some mentioned financial strains on the possibilities to insulate their homes and purchase organic groceries for example. Multiple of the answers also addressed changes that should be done by the municipality: fixing bike paths and making organic grocery shopping more accessible.

What do you do to live more sustainably?	What do you want to do?
Drink less coffee	More money for better insulation
Bringing your own cup	More vegan snack options
Planting trees	Better bike paths in Lunetten
Buying organic groceries	Less packaging for groceries
Getting Too good to go every day	More transparency on organic groceries
Solar panels, short showers, new window frames	More organic supermarkets, more affordable organic supermarkets
Walking instead of driving	Switch to electronic instead of gas stove
Reuse things and do not buy new things	Insulating home
Helping out at a vegetable garden, buying and selling local vegetables	Less flying

Second hand clothing	

Lastly, we were also giving out vouchers for Koppelsteede to all owners of a U-Pass. We gave out 3 vouchers because most of the visitors did not own a U-Pass.

Feedback on the vouchers

1. Which voucher did you get?

Koppelsteede

2. What did you buy with the voucher?

Kale, pumpkin, carrots, beets, cabbage

3. Do you want to buy organic groceries in the future? What do you need for that?

Yes, please! The farms could decrease prices for U-Pass holders.

Analysis: Regarding the vouchers a similar idea was brought forward to the other times we have gathered feedback that there is a demand for organic groceries but the thing withholding them for shopping organic is the price.

Trial with subsidized organic groceries in Lunetten, June-December 2023.

Try organic groceries yourself - Tell us what you think - And share your tips for what could be improved

Report of meeting at the limoenz foundation's giveaway shop, 3 October 2023, 9.30-12.30 hrs and 17 October, 10.15-12.15 hrs. By Ineke Malsch and Elizabete Fedčenko, ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl

On 3 October, we asked eighteen visitors to the Limoenz Foundation giveaway shop for their opinion on organic and sustainable groceries they had purchased for previously distributed gift vouchers. Ten people had been shopping at Ekovers. Three people had bought something from Koppelsteede. The overview of the reactions of these buyers can be found in the table below. Several visitors individually or in a group conversation gave their opinion on sustainable, organic and healthy food in more detail. Participants made various suggestions to make the Ekovers store more attractive. They also gave tips for other locations where we could hand out vouchers for subsidized organic groceries in other neighborhoods. Some commented on the restrictions of the U-pass, and suggested alternative discount cards, including for the regular supermarket. People also talked about giveaway cabinets in the neighborhood, and commented on community dinners held regularly in Lunetten and made suggestions to improve the healthiness of the offered food. They also proposed organising events where experience experts or professional experts could teach residents how to cook more healthy food and what is a healthy diet. Several people complained about the limited supply of fresh fruit and vegetables, and the high price of organic fruit and vegetables. If you have a diet, for example a low-sugar or low-carbohydrate diet, it is even more difficult to buy affordable healthy food. The full interview reports are below the table.

On 3 October, we handed out seventeen new vouchers with which people can buy organic groceries at the Ekovers supermarket, plus five gift vouchers from city farm Koppelsteede of Utrecht Natuurlijk. On 17th of October Elizabete went to Limoenz Foundation Giveaway shop to give away the remaining Ekovers vouchers and five Koppelsteede vouchers. Unfortunately, the Ekovers store is closing its doors on 31st of October so all participants were informed that they need to use up these vouchers before that. Additionally to distributing the vouchers, people were informed of the event on 7th of November where we

are going to discuss the project and our findings so far with all of the participants. Visitors were also informed of Warm Lunetten Energiecafe on 24 October. One person gave feedback for the Ekovers voucher (seen as entry nineteen in the table below). A lot of visitors who had not participated before received a voucher and were pleased to hear about this project. Some people brought up the concern about a food exchange shelf in Lunetten which is not upkeep properly and were inquiring if there is something we can do about this since it is a good opportunity for people with lower incomes to acquire some extra food.

On 7 November we will discuss the draft report of the project with participants who want to give their opinion on this, before we give the final report to the municipality of Utrecht. Read here the reports of June 13, July 4, August 1, September 3 and 5 and the Harvest Festival on September 17:

<https://duurzaamutrecht2030.nl/bioboodschappen>.

Preliminary analysis. One of the main points that keeps coming back up regularly in the feedback of the vouchers is that organic produce is too expensive and too difficult to access. Some of the previously heard recommendations of including organic groceries in regular supermarkets were mentioned again but it was also noted that it could be made more appealing to go to the organic supermarkets. In the case of Ekovers, it did not look inviting to participants and the atmosphere was not good in their opinion because the shelves of fruit and vegetables were half empty. Participants 7 and 8 specifically mentioned a Turkish grocery store near IBB (Sweet Greens) which always has a lot of fresh fruit and vegetables displayed by their entrance. Although this is not an organic store it still sells produce that is not packaged and also manages to appeal to those passing by the store. The participants understand that Ekovers cannot display a lot of produce in fear that it will not get bought, but this could be changed through offering discounts on fresh produce specifically, joining Too Good To Go and by working on advertising to the local community. This is something that Ekovers and other organic supermarkets could take into account and improve. Another recommendation for making sustainable living in general more accessible is promoting the possibilities of the U-Pass and providing opportunities to people who do not hold a U-Pass but still do not earn a lot of money (this can perhaps be done through establishing different levels of a U-Pass). The recommendations from this part should mostly be taken care of on the municipality level as they can give subsidies to organic supermarkets and look into the U-Pass inclusivity and whether it tackles all that should be tackled.

Another crucial point of feedback was the lack of information about healthy eating, how to cook healthy meals, how pesticides affect our produce and health and how exactly the food we buy is produced. A lot can be done on the neighborhood scale - many recommended to use community centers, second hand stores and other points where local people go for educational events such as lectures from experts on nutritious and healthy diet, cooking classes for simple, healthy meals, regular community dinners and so on. It would be useful to do this in real life events and not only in educational flyers and written information as that is much harder to remember and take in. More events could also foster a better sense of community in local neighborhoods. Furthermore there could be centralized food exchange shelves in neighborhoods that are easily accessible by all residents - this would not only minimize waste but also provide free food to those who cannot afford it. Shelves like this already exist but are poorly managed and often hidden.

Overall, from the suggestions of the participants on 3rd and 17th of October give a lot of ideas on how sustainable living and grocery shopping can be made more accessible - these changes have to take place both at the municipality and neighborhood level in order to get the best results.

Overview of the answers to questions 1-3 on 3 October and 17 October per person:

	Where?	What?	Satisfaction?
1 + 2	Ekovers	Detergents for the washing machine	good
3	Nothing yet	Want to buy unsprayed and healthy food	
4	Ekovers	Cheese and a bottle of grape juice for € 4.95.	It's a good store, with cordial people. It's expensive, but they have good stuff.
5	Ekovers	Fruit for the children – already before	It's a world of difference from regular fruit from the supermarket.
6	Not now		Comments on giveaway cabinets

also learn how to raise the children. For example, my ex-wife gave the children unhealthy food.

Organize here in the district "eat healthy" days, and cooking classes, 1-2 x a week. There is a dining table in the Musketon, but I don't go there, because the food is not healthy. The neighborhood team knows about it. On Tuesday it is coffee day, then there is someone from DOCK. Everyone can eat cheaper. They also ask others if they want to come and cook. It's important to think about what cooking style you use. You should not use all the ingredients, for example, avoid seasonings from the factory. Eat at least 50% healthy, and only a little rice, bread or pasta. If you have diabetes, intermittent fasting helps.

5. The municipality is the basis for a possible follow-up. If the municipality gives a subsidy, or shops occasionally do a discount for organic fruit and vegetables, we can buy it more often. The threshold to go to Ekovers is higher than for the supermarket, because you know that it is expensive there. If AH has a promotion for eco-bananas, it's easier to take it with you. The ordinary citizen does not easily go to Ekovers. I've been there a few times now. You see that regular customers come for certain products. I don't think people do all their shopping there. I used to walk past it, but I never went inside. With 3-4 children you don't go shopping. Stores should work more with discount promotions. [The trial with subsidized organic groceries] is a nice, but difficult project. If regular bananas cost 1 euro and organic bananas 3 euro, and you get 1 euro discount, then the ordinary ones are still cheaper. I have now had the opportunity to try out the organic products.

Great that you have incorporated the feedback on the original plan to only distribute the vouchers to U-pass holders, but also to people who earn just a little more. ... In Zuilen there was an activity only for U-pass holders. I talked to the organizer, because there is so much on offer for U-pass holders. For example, they get a free bike, free swimming lessons, or a laptop on presentation of a U-pass. My husband works, it's not a good idea to stop working to get a U-pass.

6. Further down is a giveaway cabinet. There are more in the district, but they are hidden. I think it's a nice initiative. Is it an initiative of residents, or of the municipality? [Others think it's their own initiative.] That cupboard is always full, and then empty again within a day. One such cupboard is hidden between a staircase and a bush, on the Hondsrug. Not on the shop side, but on the inhabited side. With students at the "Champignon" (?) and opposite the AH after 100 meters. With relocations, or house clearances, people often put things next

to it. These are also beautiful things. If they brought it all here to the giveaway shop, we'd perish in the stuff here.

7. I also go to the food bank. That affects what I buy. You don't get a lot of fruit and vegetables there either. You don't get enough vegetables anywhere. You get more sweets in the Netherlands. They do have soup at Ekovers, but the offer is too meager. I've only been there twice. That was my first difficulty: A at the food bank, where you get a lot of certain products, and B at such an Ekovers store: food is difficult.

7+8 [in group conversation] You should have a good supply of vegetables, that's still too little there. If you want ecological, I would focus on an ecological greengrocer, which is better than all those things around it. But those ecological vegetables are much more expensive than ordinary vegetables. People with less money can't buy it. It should be offered much more centrally. Look at the Turkish greengrocer at the IBB. In there you get the idea, here I would like to buy something. If that store is renamed Ecoplaza and remains affordable, I would like to buy there. That would really be of more use to you. Then I would eat organic much more often, and eat better. At the Turk at the IBB, the food is displayed more attractively than at Ekovers.

At Ekovers they have vegetable packages every week, you have to order them in advance. They are daily fresh products. This offer has not been clearly announced in the store. If it was advertised more clearly, I might order it.

At the IBB there is a Turkish or Moroccan shop, there is fresh fruit and vegetables in front of the door. It is not an organic store, but it does have that look. The presentation is missing at Ekovers. The shopkeeper does not buy much, because he is afraid that it will not be sold. The filled shelf gives the idea that the products are fresher. At Ekovers they do have tasty things, but you are afraid that it has been there for too long. For example, there are four apples...

9. I don't buy four apples, but always a whole bag.

8. Give people with little money a receipt to get a discount.

Ineke: Like the U-pass?

7. The U-pass is not good. I don't get a U-pass, because I earn too much, but I do go to the food bank, because I'm in debt restructuring.

8. Give a regular discount, more for fresh than for shelf life. Do not give a savings card, because you will lose it. And you have to pay something first before you can do anything with the savings card. When you have the card full, the action is also over.

9. Ekovers should actually join Too Good To Go.

8. Do they have enough supply for that?

9. I have been baking my own bread with a bread maker for six months. I follow the recipe on the packet of bread mix, use ready-made dough, or follow a recipe from a book.

7. The atmosphere in the [Ekovers] store is not very attractive. He can get more out of the store than he does now. It is a big difference from other Ecoplaza stores.

Ineke: I think he's connected to ODIN [another ecological retail chain].

7+8+9. It is not a real ODIN store, but a franchise. You can buy ODIN packages there. I have had it for a while, but sometimes the package is not there, or there are pears from Argentina in it.

10. At Koppelsteede they also have fruit and vegetables, but also cheese, soap and honey. In the autumn there is more supply, for example of pumpkins. There are fewer apples and pears this year. [At the Harvest Festival] we were allowed to search under the trees, but there were very few of them, and there weren't many in the trees. One employee said it was a bad year for apples and oranges. I also picked apples and pears in Benschop.

Ineke: where else can we hand out vouchers for organic groceries?

7+8. At the buurtbuik in Sterrenzicht you can also try. People come there every week to eat a vegetarian three-course meal. It's tasty, but you have to have a lot of seat meat. There is an Ecoplaza supermarket on the Burgemeester Reigerstraat. In the city you can eat somewhere for free every day, but not always at buurtbuik. Resto van Harte also still exists, but you have to pay for it. In Sterrenzicht the buurtbuik is every Monday evening. In my week, that works out well. I wouldn't want to eat out every day. I do like to cook, but one day a week it is nice when cooking for you.

11. If you're looking for more distribution locations, you can also go to the Salvation Army [in Kanaleneiland].

13. I bought Brazil nuts from Ekovers, they are always very expensive and even more expensive. I'm having a great-granddaughter. I would like a new voucher for Ekovers. I can't go any further, because I have to do everything on foot and have no transport. With a new voucher, I might buy nuts again, or cranberries, or cheese. It is very expensive, but then you know that it is good and tasty.

15. Is it really organic? How can you know if something is really organic? And what do you mean by organic? Is there information about the origin history of a product?

**Trial with subsidized organic groceries in Lunetten,
June-December 2023.**

**Try organic groceries yourself - Tell us what you think - And share your
tips for what could be improved**

Report of meeting at the Limoenz foundation's giveaway shop, 7 November
2023, 10.00-12.30 hrs. By Ineke Malsch, ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl

Fourteen visitors, including eleven women and three men, talked with Elizabete Fedčenko and me about their views on possible follow-up activities to the trial with subsidised organic groceries. Three people gave their individual comments and the others joined in a group conversation.

The first lady said: Ekovers is very expensive. A bread costs 3.50 euro. I thought, I have this voucher, so I will buy it anyway. If you have little money, it is too expensive. My advice to the municipality is: let supermarkets also participate in subsidised/ affordable organic groceries. I don't buy organic products at the Albert Heijn or Hoogvliet, because it is too expensive. If it would be as cheap as other products, I would buy it. There certainly is a need for affordable food. Otherwise, the foodbanks would not exist. Then, you are happy to receive something.

The community centre Musketon is a meeting place. They organise neighbourhood coffees (buurtbakkie) every Tuesday and Thursday afternoon. I sometimes go there. It is important for making contacts with other people in the neighbourhood, like we do here at the giveaway shop. If I talk to other people about organic products, I say no, because it is too expensive. In the past, I used to buy at Ekovers, but then it became more and more expensive, after they moved to a larger shop, and then Corona came.

I also buy food at discount at Lidl and Plus, and Dirk van den Broek. I don't regularly buy food at the market. Sometimes you can buy a bag of vegetables for 1 euro at the Smaragdplein. I go to the supermarkets by bus, and to the Smaragdplein by bike.

They have organic food, but I don't buy it because it is too expensive. I like organic milk and milk-products, because it tastes better. I buy Arla, which is biological, but only when it is at a discount. Other brands of milk taste less good.

I hardly eat fruit. People advise you to eat it. Now, I brought a tangerine. A net of 1 kg lasts 2 weeks. I bought Kaki fruit, but gave it to the neighbour, because

it did not taste good. I am not a vegetable person. Some vegetables I don't like, but others I do, like stews and spinach, and beet roots. I also like to buy fish at the fish stall, like herring, kibbeling, lekkerbek, but I don't like to cook the fish myself. I do care about the price, but mainly choose what I like to eat that day. Supermarkets have a broader choice, but the food looks better at a specialised organic food shop.

Lady 2 said: I received two vouchers, and bought figs and olives, which were very tasty and good. The shop was super-nice. It is a pity it was closed. In the past, I used to buy there, but it cost a lot of money. Now I cannot afford it anymore. I know there are organic shops at the Biltstraat, and there used to be one at the Springweg. I followed a cooking course and worked in a biological-dynamic restaurant at the Biltstraat. At the Vinkenburgstraat, there used to be a caravan and later a shop, an anthroposophical shop. We used to bake bread with Rozemary and other organic food. I have worked there a couple of months. I sometimes buy organic food, but not milk. I don't like milk, even though my parents had a cow and they told me it was healthy. I used to eat it with oat? (havermout). You can make lots of nice food with muesli and fruit, but I have less time now.

I used to eat a lot of meat, now I still like to eat filet americain on bread.

I would like to eat more organic fruit and vegetables if I had more money. This is different for other people, everyone's situation is different. I don't know what the municipality can do about it. My parents did grow fruit and vegetables without pesticides. For your health, it does not make so much difference. It does have an impact on the environment and on the earth. However, many people don't want vegetables with caterpillars on them. My mother used to wash the caterpillars of the vegetables before putting them on the table.

In the supermarket, I do buy organic vegetables like spitskool, when it is affordable. It does not have to look perfect. So far, it was a green shop, where I used to buy things. It depends on your situation. Promote organic food by discount actions. Sell it in larger volumes. People still prefer what looks good. If you can choose between a perfect apple and one with dents, which one would you choose? I am a flexitarian, sometimes I eat fish. I like mackerel. I also sometimes like chicken or gehakt. Recently, I haven't eaten much meat. I look at discounts. For instance, the price of filet americain was 50% reduced. I often try recipes of other cultures, in the magazine of Albert Heijn or on the mobile app.

If possible, I like to eat a warm meal at mid-day, but it is not always possible. It is more healthy. Sometimes a friend comes over for dinner, or I join a dinner at the community centre. I also sometimes go to the Buurtbuik at the Amerhof in Rivierenwijk, but it is quite far by bike. I used to go everywhere by bike, but not so often now. I used to go to the market on Tuesdays in Hoograven (Smaragdplein), but I have less energy now. I used to buy cheese on the market, but cheese, fruit and vegetables are way too expensive now. If it is affordable, I may buy organic food on the market, but my budget is limited.

Lady 3 said: I bought jam and grape juice, which was 10 euro: expensive but good. I also bought bread, from my own money. It was very tasty. The people at Ekovers were so friendly.

In the past, I also used to buy at Ekovers. I do understand that people don't like to buy there. My son is very keen on that, he is also a vegetarian. I buy organic now and then. The products are good, but it is too expensive for ordinary people. It is a pity they closed, because they could not keep it up. I thought it was expensive.

Biological meat is good, but at least 1-2 times as expensive as ordinary meat. I don't go to the market regularly anymore. I still like to buy cheese there. I love it.

I would like to buy such bread more often, it was very tasty. I am sorry for those people, I did buy some extra things from my own money, but then the money ran out.

Couple 4+5 (M+F) asked if the trial was limited to Lunetten. [so far, yes, but we will try to extend it to other neighbourhoods. Elizabete presented the findings of the trial so far.]

The greengrocer at IBB does not sell organic fruit and vegetables, but is fresh and presented attractively.

Ekoplaza has a bigger choice in organic fruits and vegetables, and it is presented more attractively. They also sell packaged products. At the Kanaalstraat in Lombok, many shops present their fruit and vegetables on the street, which also looks more attractive.

The best location for a specialised organic shop is next to a supermarket, as was the case with Ekovers. However, it did not look attractive enough. It is too expensive.

Bring it out in a good way, demonstrating you have a good shop. Where people don't go, results in a self fulfilling prophecy.

The municipality could subsidise fresh produce in organic supermarkets. Or the shopkeeper could give customers who have bought several times a coupon – Buy x times, get something for free.

Comments on the proposal for the follow-up project:

Buy one, give one: There are a lot of similar initiatives, but then you pay for a shelf-stable product. One problem with advance payment of fresh products, is that the shopkeeper may bring leftovers to the food bank. A better alternative was if they hand out vouchers at the food bank, which the clients can use to buy fresh food they want during the following week.

Don't limit it to seasonal food. In the season you get too many tomatoes, onions or cucumbers.

We intend to go to the foodbank first and ask the clients what they would like. That is good, but the list should change with the season, and it should include a variety.

The buurtbuik gets the leftovers from the foodbank at the red cross at the Koningsweg, plus some extra supplies, and uses it to cook a nice three-course meal. This should be taken into account.

Women 6,7 and 8 joined: Will the municipality collaborate with this? If an organic shop has leftovers, they want to get rid of it. Is it feasible for the municipality to pay for this? Currently, the food bank gets leftovers. As a client you are happy to get something fresh.

Will it be feasible to deliver non-seasonal produce? It is unavoidable that there is a lot of that.

The problem with the food at the food bank is that it is often already past the selling date or even half rotten.

If you get fresh produce once a week, it has to remain fresh for the rest of the week.

A better option is like the trial with the vouchers we ran: Hand out vouchers, allowing the receivers to buy something fresh they want, not just vegetables. You should be able to spread your shopping over several days. For example: on Saturday you hand out a voucher, which is valid for a week, from Wednesday until the next Wednesday, only for fresh food.

Herbs are already off, beans are already rotten, and you get lots of food with sugar in it.

It is not the food bank's fault. Too good to go made it more difficult for them to get fresh food.

Person 9: I saw a challenge for the food bank. I also buy too good to go.

At the food bank, you do get fruit and vegetables, but not a lot. In the shops it is very expensive.

There is a shop near the Makro, where you get lots of vegetables and fruit for 5 euro.

Person 10. I went to Spain. In a restaurant, people paid for an extra breakfast, lunch or dinner, and the receipt was put in a jar near the entrance. Another visitor can pick up such a receipt, show it and gets served the meal. But only if someone paid for it in advance.

Group conversation: It is like a coffee in America, the same system.

Perhaps you can engage with vegan and organic restaurants and cafes, and supermarkets. I pay 2 euro for fruit and vegetables, they print the ticket and another person can pick it up.

At the food bank, you get everything for free, or someone has paid it for you.

Personally, I give sardines and milk I get from the food bank to someone else. If I tell them, I am a vegetarian, I get nothing. I don't get vegetables, but lots of rice, pasta etc. 1 lettuce and a couple of vegetables. Nothing else. Or if it is the potato-season, bags of potatoes, or loads of onions. 4-5 weeks in a row: onions. Or loads of Brussels sprouts.

40 pots of peanut butter, etc. The cupboards are overflowing.

People do give feedback to the volunteers at the food bank, they have regular conversations. Many people complain that they don't get enough vegetables.

I swap my peanut butter with people who do go shopping.

I exchanged 2 bags of apples.

This is not allowed.

The best option is to let someone pay for someone else in advance, letting the person choose by themselves what they want to buy. Don't let the shopkeeper choose the products they want to give to the food bank.

Woman 11: I have lunched 3x at the children's farm. It was a real outing, you can sit there and enjoy looking at the kids. I also bought fresh vegetables and home-made sambal there. Cosyness (gezelligheid) is important, and that you can go there and take a seat in the sun. I am not entitled to the food bank, because I have a WAJONG benefit (uitkering), and my income is just a bit too high. It makes a difference for me if I can sit somewhere to have lunch, coffee with quiches and a salad for exactly 10 euro. You can stay as long as you like.

Group conversation: I have 10 euro for my shopping, so I can buy rice with packaged sauce. Fresh food is too expensive.

At the children's farm, the vegetables are much cheaper: knolselderij, prei (leek), and other vegetables. They only have seasonal vegetables.

In the summer, the volkstuintjes (allotment gardens) near the children's farm also have vegetables.

Woman 12: wants to talk about a give away cupboard, opposite the Taiba shop. This is working very well. She sometimes put stuff there, which was gone the next day. The problem is that noone seems to be responsible for the cupboard. One time, it was stolen. Someone chained a new cupboard to the wall, but this was also stolen. A cupboard from board was rotten, a table toppled over.

Group discussion: Is Duurzaam Utrecht 2030 only active in Lunetten? [No, all over the city.]

Could the municipality place a solid cupboard where people can put things to give away in? It should be anchored to the wall, so people don't take it away. And then someone should inform the municipality if something needs replacement. The problem is if nobody is personally responsible, nobody will take care of it. Bookshelves are usually placed in someone's garden, and are maintained by the owner of the garden.

In other neighbourhood, there are also cupboards where people put food in to give away. For example at the Ruigenhoeklaan.

I know of a shop which went bankrupt in another city, and then volunteers took over and ran it. Could this be an option here, to take over small shops and let volunteers run them?

A woman reported what she bought for the voucher at Ekovers: tasty organic bread, a bottle of juice you don't get at the supermarket, from regional farms (streeksap). A replacement of coffee, with spices and cinnamon, which you have to heat. I also bought a piece of cheese, like at Koppelsteede.

Men 13 and 14 joined the group conversation: Albert Heijn (AH) has a lot of organic food, mostly bought by Yups, who may be able to afford to give something away.

Sometimes you don't have much time for shopping, and AH is not always more expensive.

I always buy raisins at AH, because they are better than at other supermarkets. At AH they use sun flower oil, and at other shops cotton oil. Sometimes, they are treated with sulfur and then you must wash it off, so it gets into the water. Organic raisins are without sulfur.

A man reported that he was just in time to use the voucher at Ekovers, before it closed. It is too expensive, not everyone can buy there. Only with the voucher it

was possible. Ten euro for half a litre of oil, compared to 5-6 euro at AH. How can you manage to buy all that organically?

Large supermarket chains can lower the prices. The government can stimulate it by lowering taxes on organic food. Special shops ran by unemployed people or volunteers, managed by a foundation, could also be an option.

Another man was mildly skeptical of the idea to ask consumers to pay extra. Another option was that farmers sometimes overproduce, or the produce is not 100% perfect, but still consumable. Even though AH sometimes sells imperfect fruits and vegetables, farmers can not always sell it to the supermarkets. Could you get in touch with regional farmers in the province of Utrecht, to deliver it to the food bank? It just has to be picked up. This limits “doordraaien” (throwing away). Then you get big amounts of produce. It could also be linked to a national webportal voorkomdoordraaien.nl. The farmers could offer it at a reduced price (less than half), or if they want to give it for free, that is also welcome.

The group conversation continued: Koppelsteede also has cheap seasonal vegetables, soap, milk and meat.

Small shops cannot buy their supplies so cheaply, because they cannot make such cheap deals with suppliers

But this is not always the case, some shops at the Kanaalstraat are cheaper than AH.

Don't just use small shops, but also work with large supermarkets, like AH, Hoogvliet, Lidl. They already supply the food banks, and sometimes ask consumers to buy packaged food for the food bank. For them it is a barrier if they have to hire extra personnel. You could ask if it is ok if people come to fetch the leftover products. A pick up service is needed, with volunteers, and a budget for petrol or electricity.

In Turkey, I saw long queues in front of the bakery. They told me people could get free bread. Some people pay the baker to give a specific number of people bread. Every city has poor people. I did not see greengrocers in Turkey.

For us, vegetables are also very important.

The whole sale buyers of supermarkets go to farmers and buy tangerines or tomatoes, apples or potatoes, but only the ones that look good. The farmers could supply the less good looking produce to the food bank.

Another option is to teach people how to preserve things, like zucchini, or to grow herbs in your house, or things like spring onions. My God mother grows tomatoes on her balcony.

Appendix 2: Questionnaire for the participants

Try organic groceries yourself - Tell us what you think - And share your tips for what could be improved.

Questions:

- 1) For which store did you receive the gift card?

- 2) What did you buy with the voucher?

- 3) What do you think of the products you have purchased?

- 4) Do you want to buy organic or sustainable groceries more often? What do you need for that?

- 5) What can the municipality of Utrecht do to help you buy organic groceries?

- 6) Do you have any other tips for us?

More information:

What do we do? We hand out vouchers with which you can buy organic and sustainable products yourself.

Would you like to answer the questions on this sheet anonymously? Or would you like to give us your opinion in a conversation? Participation is voluntary and anonymous. You can always withdraw immediately. We do not write down your name.

When do we hand out the vouchers? On Tuesday mornings 13 June, 4 July, 1 August, 5 September, and 3 October 2023, between 9:00 and 12:00.

Where do we hand out the vouchers? At the giveaway shop of Stichting Limoenz, Treek 15 in Lunetten.

Who is it for? Residents with a small purse.

What do we do with your comments? We collect them anonymously in a report.

Debriefing: On Tuesday morning, November 7, 2023, we will talk to you about this report in the giveaway shop. We will process your reactions and suggestions in the final report. Those who participate in this debriefing will receive a volunteer allowance.

In December 2023 we will publish the final report for the municipality of Utrecht and anyone who wants to know more. You will also get a copy if you wish.

News about the project appears on the website: <https://duurzaamutrecht2030.nl/> Would you like to know more or participate yourself? Let me know: ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl.